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THIRD GENERATION SEMICONDUCTORS

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ПОЛУПРОВОДНИКИ ТРЕТЬЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ

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Abstract

With the increasingly serious problems of environmental pollution and global warming, the research and application of renewable energy sources have attracted unprecedented attention. Among them, semiconductor technology, as an important tool for promoting green energy transformation, is attracting more and more attention from scientific research and industry. In particular, third-generation semiconductor materials are revolutionizing the field of renewable energy due to their superior physical properties and application prospects.

With the rapid development of technology, third-generation semiconductors are being studied because they bring about significant changes in industries such as computers, mobile devices, lighting, etc. manufacturing. Up to now, third-generation semiconductors have been applied to many fields due to their irreplaceable physical properties.

The application of third-generation semiconductors, namely GaN and SiC, is analyzed. Their characteristics, including advantages and disadvantages, are discussed by reviewing the results of relevant research. At the same time, a comparison is made between third-generation semiconductors and second and first-generation semiconductors. The physical properties, final marketing, and limitations, the advantages and disadvantages of each semiconductor are analyzed and suggestions are made to overcome the shortcomings through application. Finally, future development is predicted [5].

Аннотация

В связи с растущими проблемами загрязнения окружающей среды и глобального потепления исследования и применение возобновляемых источников энергии привлекают беспрецедентное внимание. Среди них полупроводниковые технологии как важный инструмент содействия переходу на зеленую энергетику привлекают все большее внимание со стороны научных исследователей и промышленности. В частности, полупроводниковые материалы третьего поколения производят революцию в области возобновляемой энергетики благодаря своим превосходным физическим свойствам и перспективам применения.

В связи с быстрым развитием технологий все больше внимания уделяется изучению полупроводников третьего поколения, поскольку они используются в компьютерах, мобильных устройствах, освещении и т. д. Это вызывает значительные изменения в отрасли, например, в производстве. На сегодняшний день полупроводники третьего поколения нашли применение во многих областях благодаря своим бесценным физическим свойствам.

Проанализировано применение полупроводников третьего поколения, а именно GaN и SiC. Их характеристики, включая преимущества и недостатки, обсуждаются путем анализа результатов соответствующих исследований. При этом проводится сравнение полупроводников третьего поколения с полупроводниками второго и первого поколений. Сравнивая физические свойства, конечный рынок, производство и ограничения, анализируются преимущества и недостатки каждого полупроводника, и вносятся предложения по преодолению недостатков путем применения. Наконец, прогнозируется будущее развитие [5].

Keywords: mobile devices, telecommunications, computer, electronics, radiation.

Ключевые слова: мобильные устройства, телекоммуникации, компьютеры, электроника, радиация.

Electronics is one of the modern directions of science and technology, which is directly related to every sphere of human activity. Therefore, the study of the basics of electronics to one extent or another is included in the curricula of most technical specialties. The development of electronics has had a positive impact on the development of cybernetics, which deals with the issues of control and communication in machines and living organisms, and the creation of high-speed computers [1].

A new stage in the development of the technical level of the element base of electronics is associated with the transition to integrated microcircuits, which are the basis of advanced computers. Unlike the other materials under consideration, which changed our world primarily through evolution, semiconductors have caused a technological revolution in many areas. They have created the possibilities of computers and telecommunications, systems that process and transmit large amounts of information for business, healthcare, education, science, military and recreational purposes. Semiconductor devices have added sensitivity, power and reliability to electronic sensing, measuring and control functions, as well as to all consumer electronics equipment [2].

What are the third generation semiconductors? Semiconductor materials can be divided into three generations depending on the order of research, development and application. The first generation semiconductors were mainly composed of elements such as silicon and germanium, which are widely used in electronic devices. The second generation semiconductors are mainly compound semiconductors such as gallium nitride, silicon carbide, etc., which are widely used in high-frequency and high-power electronic devices because they can handle high power and frequency. The third generation semiconductors are represented by gallium nitride (GaN), silicon carbide (SiC), aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃), etc., which have higher voltage, temperature resistance, radiation resistance, resistance and radiation resistance, making them ideal for new generation energy systems.

Solar power generation system. The use of third generation semiconductors in solar power generation systems has significantly improved efficiency and stability. In photovoltaic cells, the cell conversion efficiency of traditional silicon-based materials is usually 15% to 20%. The use of third-generation semiconductor materials such as gallium nitride and silicon carbide can even reach 30%. At the same time, due to the high temperature and high voltage resistance of third-generation semiconductors, the durability and service life of photovoltaic elements have been greatly improved, and the maintenance and upgrade costs of photovoltaic power generation systems have been reduced [6].

Although we have now transitioned to third-generation semiconductor materials, first- and second-generation semiconductor materials have not been eliminated and are still widely used. Why has the emergence of the second generation not replaced the first generation? Can third-generation semiconductors completely replace traditional semiconductor

materials? Silicon and compound semiconductors are two complementary materials. In the application of semiconductors, the two are often combined to benefit from each other, so that products that meet higher requirements such as high reliability, high speed, and defense military products are produced. Therefore, first- and second-generation semiconductor materials are in a state of long-term commonality.

The third generation of wide bandgap semiconductor materials has many excellent properties that can overcome the development bottleneck of the first and second generation semiconductor materials. With the development of technology, the third generation is expected to completely replace the first and second generation semiconductor materials [6].

The third generation of semiconductor materials are wide bandgap materials (e.g., $\geq 2.3\text{eV}$). They usually have high breakdown electric field, high thermal conductivity, high electron saturation degree, and higher radiation resistance. Therefore, they are used in the manufacture of high-temperature, high-frequency, radiation-resistant, and high-power devices. Typical materials are silicon carbide (SiC), gallium nitride (GaN), aluminum nitride (AlN), and zinc oxide (ZnO).

Wind power generation system. The use of third-generation semiconductors in the power conversion and control systems of wind power systems has a positive effect on the overall efficiency and stability. The power conversion and control system of wind turbines requires power equipment that can withstand high voltage and high frequency. Power equipment using third-generation semiconductor materials can not only improve efficiency, but also reduce failure rates and improve system reliability. In addition, the radiation resistance and high temperature resistance of third-generation semiconductors enable wind power systems to operate stably in harsh environments [6].

Conclusion

1. The widespread use of third-generation semiconductors provides strong technical support for the efficient use of renewable energy sources. By improving the conversion efficiency and stability of photovoltaic cells, wind turbines and other equipment, as well as the efficiency of power grids and energy storage systems, the conversion of green energy has been significantly advanced.

2. Third-generation semiconductors not only reduce the cost of unit energy generation and make renewable energy more competitive, but also provide an opportunity to solve the global energy crisis. The latter reduces the frequency and reduces the impact on the environment. In addition, the use of third-generation semiconductors also reduces energy consumption during equipment operation, which further reduces the burden on the environment.

3. Finally, the use of third-generation semiconductors in energy storage and power grids makes the use of renewable energy more efficient and sustainable. This goes a long way in solving the problem of unstable renewable energy supply caused by weather and seasonal changes.

4. In summary, the emergence and application of third-generation semiconductor materials has revolutionized the field of renewable energy and provided us with strong technical support to enter the era of green energy. Although there are still some problems in production and application, such as cost, process and other problems, these problems are expected to be solved with the development of technology and the expansion of the industrial scale.

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